

STRESSORS IN WORK ENVIRONMENT, COPING MECHANISM AND THE TEACHING COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

Teaching is the most profoundly important profession. Teaching is greatly rewarding and probably the most challenging. This study focused on stressors in work environment, coping mechanism and the teaching competence particularly in public elementary schools' teachers in Sto. Tomas South District, Division of Batangas. This study is a descriptive-correlational kind of research, 170 respondents were teaching in Sto. Tomas South District conducted last April. The study uses a survey questionnaire through the use of google form for the easier distribution and collection of data. Based on the findings, the stressors in work environment are significantly related to teaching competence. On the other hand, coping mechanisms are significantly related to teaching competence. The researcher study recommended that regular assessment of stress management level may be conducted for preventive measures in every school in able to lessen or alleviate the stress level of the teacher. The supervisors may consider planning, organizing, conducting seminars, training or workshop on how to cope with stress that the teacher encounters in their jobs.

Keywords: Stressors, work environment, coping mechanism, teaching competence, profoundly